

Direct joining of CFRTP and Aluminum Sheets

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ABSTRACT

In this study, mechanical joining method between anchor processed aluminium sheet and CFRTP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermo-Plastic) sheet without rivets by using induction heating for carbon fiber is suggested, and joining strength were investigated. The strength of the joint was evaluated by a tensile shear test. As a Result, it was shown that the joining strength when arranging the anchors in a square can be predicted from the strength of the anchor alone and the number of rows. In addition, it was found that even with the same arrangement, the strength changes when the distance between anchors changes. The cause was clarified by FEM analysis. In FEM analysis when using high-strength metal as the anchor, and that it can obtain a higher joining strength. From the cross section observation results, it was found that the metal and the carbon fiber were in direct contact with each other. As a result of evaluating concerns about electrolytic corrosion, it was found that when accelerating voltage is applied, corrosion is occurred.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays lightweight materials such as aluminium alloy or magnesium alloy, also High Tensile Strength Steel have been used for weight reduction of motor vehicles. On the other hand, Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRPs) have remarkable high specific strength, however they have been only adopted airplane or parts of high grade cars because of its high cost. In these days, thanks to various researches problems concerning of CFRPs applications for motor vehicles have been decreasing, and then multi material including CFRP could be used in motor vehicle designs. Generally it is difficult to join between different materials. In many cases, sheets made of different materials are usually joined by using rivets. Though there are a lot of reports about joining between CFRP and metals, the joining strength depends on the strength of rivets or the matrix material of CFRP. In this study, mechanical joining method between anchor processed aluminium sheet and CFRTP sheet without rivets by using induction heating for carbon fiber is suggested, and joining strength were investigated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Joining procedure and tensile test

In this study, joining method between CFRTP which matrix polymer is PMMA and aluminum sheet is discussed. First of all, a claw shape mechanical anchors were processed in aluminum sheet as shown in Fig.1. Each anchor is a height of 0.87mm, a width of 1mm, a thickness of 0.5mm, an angle of 60 degrees (Fig.2). These anchors were locates in every 1mm.

CFRTP sheet was heated up to PMMA's softening point which around 150 degree C, by high frequency induction heating, the melt CFRTP and aluminum anchor were pressed and joint each other (Fig.3). The pressing load was about 500N and holding time was about 6 minutes.

The jig for processing anchors can manufacture 25 pattern of rectangular array including square shape. To investigate the influence of anchor's layout on joining strength, tensile shear test of 20

pattern changed the layout were conducted. Then tensile shear tests were performed for evaluation of joining strength. The specimen used for tensile shear test is shown in Fig.4. 0

Figure 1: Anchors processed in aluminum sheet

Figure 2: Size of each anchor

Figure 3: Overview of the joining method

Figure 4: Specimens for tensile test

2.2 Results of tensile test

Test results are shown in Fig.5, the values in the table are strength of the anchor's each claw. Joining strength of square array is shown in Fig.6. From these results, square joining strength σ can be approximated with a formula shown as below.

$$\sigma = \frac{F}{n^{2.1} \log n \frac{2n-1}{n}} \quad n : \text{line number} \quad F: \text{strength of each claw}$$

Next, as shown in Fig. 7 (a), anchors of 3mm interspace were fabricated and tensile test were conducted to investigate an influence of anchor's distance on joining strength. The strength after tensile test of 9 claws, square shape was shown in Fig.8.

Strength of each claw[N]	1	2	3	4	5
1	50.9	64.3	55.5	54.2	45.4
2	69.5	51.0	54.5	54.6	
3	48.6	57.5	48.6	53.4	50.1
4			57.9	43.8	43.0
5			45.4	49.0	49.0

Figure 5: Results of tensile test

Figure 6: Joining strength of square array

(a) Sparse

(b) Dense

Figure 8: Compare of sparse and dense

Figure 7: Specimens of dissimilar distance

According to the value of Fig.5, it is found that joining strength was not proportional to the number and the arrangement of anchor's claw. It is also found that joining strength is clearly affected by interspace of anchors. After tensile test, it was observed that anchor's deformation decreases as going to the anchor behind and small gap was made between the sheets (Fig.9). The gap generation suggested the decrease of strength of sparse specimen due to decrease amount of anchor's deformation by peel of entire of sheet.

Figure 9: Specimen of after tensile test (sparse)

2.3 Observation of the cross-section

The interface between carbon fiber and aluminum anchor was observed by SEM. Joining specimens were filled in embedding-resin, after curing specimen was cut along the cutting line as shown in Fig.10. Fig.11.and Fig.12 shows to the image by SEM. From Fig. 12, some orthogonal fiber against anchor was broken. However, as for the parallel fiber against anchor, damage could particularly not be observed.

Figure 10: Cutting line for SEM observation of cross section between aluminum plate and CFRTP sheet

Figure 11: Cross section of joining specimen

Figure 12: SEM observation of interface between carbon fibers and aluminum anchor

3 ANALYSIS OF JOINING MECHANISM BY FEM

3.1 Analysis condition

To clarify the mechanism of joining strength, FEM analysis was performed. We can obtain the prospect of increasing the joining strength from results of analysis. MSC Marc is used for analysis. First, reproduce the deformation behavior before leading to a break. Second, compare the consistency between the analysis results and experimental results. The analysis model shown in Fig.13 was modeled using 3D-CAD as the same size as the used test specimen, and mesh was generated using MSC Marc. For the physical properties of aluminum, the Stress-Strain curve diagram was obtained by uniaxial tensile test. As for the physical properties of CFRTP were found to be only orthogonal fiber from the result of cross section observation, physical properties of orthogonality anisotropic elastoplasticity were obtained from the approximation formula (1)[2]. The physical properties used are shown in Table 1. About boundary condition, CFRTP was fixed and forced displacement such as pulling 0.5 mm at 1/sec in the Z direction of the anchor was given. Compare the reaction force at this

result with the test force of the experiment result. Analysis was conducted to reveal the deformation behavior. Fig.14 shows a comparison of tensile load between the analysis results and the experimental results. From this comparison, it can be said that the analysis conditions simulate the experiment well.

Figure 13: 3D analysis model

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_L &= E_{fL}V_f + E_m(1 - V_f) \\
 E_T &= (1 - C) \frac{E_{fT}E_m}{E_mV_f + E_{fT}(1 - V_f)} + C\{E_{fT}V_f + E_m(1 - V_f)\} \\
 \nu_L &= (1 - C)\{\nu_{fL}V_f + \nu_m(1 - V_f)\} + C \frac{\nu_{fL}E_{fT}V_f + \nu_mE_m(1 - V_f)}{E_{fT}V_f + E_m(1 - V_f)} \\
 \nu_T &= \nu_L(E_T/E_L) \\
 G_{LT} &= (1 - C) \frac{G_{fLT}G_m}{G_mV_f + G_{fLT}(1 - V_f)} + C\{G_{fLT}V_f + G_m(1 - V_f)\} \\
 C &= 0.4V_f - 0.025
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Engineering constant		
E_{11}	[GPa]	136.65
E_{22}	[GPa]	2.3
E_{33}	[GPa]	2.3
G_{12}	[GPa]	60.5
G_{23}	[GPa]	1.15
G_{31}	[GPa]	60.5
ν_{12}	–	0.3
ν_{23}	–	0.3
ν_{31}	–	0.005

Table 1: Material properties of CFRTP

Figure 14: Comparison of tensile load between experiment and analysis result

3.2 Influence of distance between anchors

From the experimental results in Fig. 8, it was suggested that the distance between the anchors affected the joining strength. In order to clarify the effect of distance between anchors on joining strength, analysis was performed by changing the distance of two anchors allocated in series. The four models are designed. An overview of the model is shown in Fig. 15. The analysis conditions are as described in section 3.1. Deformation behavior of aluminum after the analysis is shown in Fig. 16, it was found that the peeling amount of the front end of the aluminum plate increased as the distance between the anchors increased. Fig. 17 shows a graph of the peeling amount. From this result, it is considered that the cause of the strength degradation with low density anchor is due to decrease in deformation amount of anchor.

Figure 15: Anchor design with changing distance for FEM analysis

(a) Analysis result of D1

(b) Analysis result of D7

Figure 16: FEM analysis of tensile test

Figure 17: Displacement Y amount of front end of aluminum sheet for Y direction

3.3 Iron anchor

Analysis of changing the anchor material for getting the prospect of high joining strength were performed. We will expect to improve the joining strength when using an iron anchor which could not be used in the experiment because it was difficult to fabricate the anchor. The material used for analysis is high tension steel plate. The physical properties used are shown in Table 2. Fig. 18 shows a comparison of analysis results. As a result of changing to high tensile strength steel plate instead of aluminum sheet, the reaction force value improved 46%. From this result, it was suggested that the joining strength of the present technology depends on the physical properties of the base metal and further strengthening can be possible.

Engineering constant		
Young's modulus	[GPa]	203
Poisson's ratio	–	0.3

Table 2: Material properties of High tensile strength steel

Figure 18: Comparison of tensile test between iron and aluminum by FEM analysis

4 GALVANIC CORROSION

From the SEM image in section 2.3, the anchor and the carbon fiber are directly contacted. Therefore, corrosion may occur between the anchor and the carbon fiber. For the evaluation of galvanic corrosion, a corrosion acceleration test in 3 wt% salt water is conducted. The chemical composition of the solute is shown in Table 3. As the test piece, one to which the lead wire is connected is used as the joint (Fig. 19). Anchors array of 2 × 5 and 5 × 5 are tested. Lead wires dipped in salt water are insulated with resin. A schematic diagram of the acceleration test apparatus is shown in Fig.20. Voltage of 2V is applied from the stabilized power source and specimens were left for 50 hours, and then components of corrosion products were analyzed by X-ray fluorescence analysis.

Chemical composition (wt%)					
Br	Si	S	K	Cl	Ca
0.10	0.02	7.59	3.60	81.17	7.49

Table 3: Chemical composition of solute by X-ray fluorescence analysis

Figure 19: Specimen of corrosion test

Figure 20: Apparatus of corrosion test

The test piece after the corrosion test is shown in Fig.21. Referring to Fig. 21, corrosion is progressed in 2×5 specimen compared with 5×5 specimen. It was often observed that aluminum sheets were heavily damaged by chemical degradation. This is considered that the resistance is higher as the number of anchors is smaller and the potential difference due to the acceleration voltage increased. The collected precipitate was dried and subjected to fluorescent X-ray analysis, and the results are shown in Table 4. Since aluminum was detected from the precipitate, it was suggested that aluminum hydroxide was produced as a corrosion product [1].

Figure 21: Specimens of after corrosion test

Chemical composition (wt%)					
Al	Si	S	K	Cl	Ca
4.80	0.15	5.74	3.97	81.47	3.56

Table 4: Chemical composition of precipitate by X-ray fluorescence analysis

5 CONCLUSION

Mechanical joining between CFRTP and aluminum sheet were carried out. And joining strength is almost as same as that of adhesive. From the results of the tensile test, it was possible to derive an equation for predicting the joining strength in the case of square shape. It was found that the joining strength varied not only by the number of anchors but also by arrangement and distance. As a result of FEM analysis, it was found that when the distance between anchors increased, the peeling amount of the plate increased and the strength in the shear direction decreased. As a result of analysis by changing material of anchor, it was shown that higher joining strength can be achieved. As a result of evaluation of electrolytic corrosion, it was suggested that the rate of corrosion progression might change depending on the number of anchors. As for the electric corrosion, detailed investigation including the influence on strength etc. is necessary.

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